

Supplemental Fig. S1, continued

Suppl. Fig. S1 (related to Fig. 1). **Multimodal imaging of islet aggregation with duct-islet cell cluster in PDAC surgical margin.** (A-I) and (J-R) are two examples of the coexistence of islet aggregation, PanIN, acinar atrophy, and fibrosis in the surgical margin distal to PDAC (case No. 1628870 and 4442070). In *G*, *H*, *P*, *Q*, varying amounts of mucin were observed in the duct lesions. In *I* and *R*, the high-resolution images identify the duct (CK7⁺)-islet (insulin⁺ or glucagon⁺) cell cluster. Green, CK7; blue, insulin; magenta, glucagon; white, nuclei.